

Exploration in the Age of AI

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Paper Outline

<p>Argument of this Paper</p>	<p>This provides a critical review of exploration across scientific disciplines, incorporating insights from the recent AI revolution. The paper offers new thoughts on creating a more nuanced understanding of exploration and its trade-offs, highlighting the opportunities and challenges presented by the judicious use of AI.</p>
<p>Contributions</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. This study introduces the first detailed collection of definitions across exploration, education, decision-making science, among others, setting the base for cross-disciplinary research. 2. Next, it highlights and addresses the challenges and compromises in exploration, especially their impact on early childhood education, enriching the conversation around educational practices. 3. Subsequently, it delves into the potential benefits and risks of artificial intelligence (AI) in exploration, contributing to discussions on AI's ethical and social ramifications. 4. Finally, this study outlines potential future research areas on exploration and its integration with other disciplines, advocating for collaborative and comprehensive approaches.
<p>Nuancing Exploration: Six Trade-offs</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Specific vs Diverse Exploration 2. Delayed/Instant Gratification 3. Adaptive vs Maladaptive 4. Mood Dependency (Arousal vs Valence) and Persistence/Stability Vs Flexibility 5. Breadth-depth (BD) tradeoff 6. Directed/strategic and random exploration 7. The means-ends, what-vs-how distinction (Process vs Outcome)
<p>AI: Prospects and Limitations</p>	<p>A. Prospects</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Improve the execution of administrative functions and streamlining communication 2. Scaffold and accelerate both scientific discovery and scientific reasoning within the practical setting 3. Making AI a Socratic partner <p>B. Limitations</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Uberautomation/delegation to AI 2. Threats to safety, digital security and privacy of the children's lives 3. Loss of connection to nature and movement for children 4. Acceleration of inequalities, colonialistic value dominance, and competitive behavior for children

	5. Loss from an early childhood perspective of traditional play and human contact/opposition processing, tolerance, even love
Research Prospects	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Empirically test and verify the long-term effects of different modes of exploration 2. Clarify the process of exploration 3. Create AI-friendly posthuman ECEC 4. Surface exploration synergies between artificial curiosity and natural curiosity
Final Words	Exploration is the Daughter of Curiosity. It is the engineering “how” to its philosophical “why”.

Studies Worth Reading

Exploration Dilemmas

- Eliassen, S., Jørgensen, C., Mangel, M., & Giske, J. (2007). Exploration or exploitation: Life expectancy changes the value of learning in foraging strategies. *Oikos*, 116, 513–523. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.2006.0030-1299.15462.x>.
- Gershman, S. J. 2018. "Deconstructing the Human Algorithms for Exploration." *Cognition* 173 (August 2017): 34–42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cognition.2017.12.014>.
- Ivancovsky, T., S. Baror, and M. Bar. 2023. "A Shared Novelty-Seeking Basis for Creativity and Curiosity." *Behavioral and Brain Sciences*. :1-61. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0140525X23002807>.
- Wilson, R. C., Geana, A., White, J. M., Ludvig, E. A., & Cohen, J. D. (2014). Humans use directed and random exploration to solve the explore-exploit dilemma. *Journal of Experimental Psychology. General*, 143(6), 2074–2081. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0038199>

Children and Exploration

- Gopnik, A. (2020). Childhood as a solution to explore-exploit tensions. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series B, Biological Sciences*, 375(1803), 20190502. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2019.0502>

- Hutt, C., Tyler, S., Hutt, C., & Christopherson, H. (1989). *Play, exploration and learning*. London: Routledge.
- Schulz, L. (2015). Infants explore the unexpected. *Science* 348 (6230): 42–43. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aabo582>

Exploration and the AI Revolution

- Bostrom, N. 2014. *Superintelligence: Paths, Dangers, Strategies*. Oxford University Press.
- Dubey, R., & Griffiths, T. L. (2020). Understanding exploration in humans and machines by formalizing the function of curiosity. *Current Opinion in Behavioral Sciences*, 35, 118–124. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cobeha.2020.07.008>
- Kalluri, Pratyusha. 2020. ‘Don’t Ask If Artificial Intelligence Is Good or Fair, Ask How It Shifts Power’. *Nature* 583 (7815): 169–169. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-020-02003->

Visual Artifacts

ex-plōro, āvi, ātum, 1, v. a.,

I. to search out, seek to discover, to examine, investigate, explore (class.; in Cic. esp. freq. in the part. perf. and P. a.; syn.: speculor, scitor, sciscitor, percontor, quaero, interrogo).

I. In gen.

(α). With acc.: “explora rem totam,” Cic. Att. 6, 8, 5:

“fugam domini,” Cic. Verr. 2, 5, 17, § 44: “ambitum Africae,” Plin. 5, 1,

1, § 8: “altera (manus) motu caecum iter explorat,” Ov. M. 10, 456:

“vehiculorum onera,” Suet. Tib. 18: “glebas gustu,” Col. 2, 2, 20:

“panis potionisque bonitatem gustu,” Tac. A. 12, 66 et saep.:

“ad explorandum idoneum locum castris,” for choosing out, Caes. B. C. 1,

81, 1: “insidias,” to seek out, Verg. G. 3, 537.—

(β). With rel. clause: “explorare, qui homines inhabitarent,” Petr. 116:

“apud se explorare, an expediat sibi consilium,” Dig. 17, 1, 2 fin.:

“exploratum est, ubi controversia incipiat,” Quint. 7, 1, 8.—

b. In the part. perf., examined, ascertained, known:

“exploratum et provisum,” Plaut. Capt. 3, 4, 110:

“jam explorata nobis sunt ea, quae, etc.,” Cic. Rep. 1, 13:

“perspecta et explorata perscribere,” id. Att. 3, 15, 8; cf.:

“res non incertis jactatae rumoribus, sed compertae et exploratae,” Liv. 42,

13, 1: “de numero eorum omnia se habere explorata Remi dicebant,” Caes.

B. G. 2, 4, 4; id. B. C. 2, 31, 5.—In abl. neutr. absol.: explorato, it being

ascertained, i. e. when he knew: “explorato, jam profectos amicos,” Tac. H.

2, 49.

Lewis and Short (1879), *A Latin Dictionary*: “Exploro”

432 sqq. ; Thes. V 2, 1738 s. u. Uniquement usitée dans les souscriptions de manuscrits avec le sens de « finit, s'achève ». V. *plectō*.

explōdō : v. *plaudō*.

explōrō, -ās, -ānī, -ātum:, -āre : battre le terrain, reconnaître, explorer (sens propre et figuré) ; et par suite « faire l'essai ou l'épreuve de » (par rapprochement avec *experior*). Ancien, usuel et classique.

Dérivés et composés : *explōrātor*, qui dans la langue militaire a pris le sens d' « éclaireur » et aussi d' « espion » ; *explōrātrix* (Cassien) ; *explōrātiō* ; *explōrātīrius* ; *inexplōrātus* (T.-L.). Les étymologies anciennes ne séparent pas *explōrō* de *plōrō*, *implōrō*, mais il doit y avoir beaucoup de fantaisie dans une étymologie comme celle de Festus, P. F. 69, 21 : *explorare antiquos pro exclamare usos, sed postea prospicere et certum cognoscere coepit significare. Itaque speculator ab exploratore hoc distat quod speculator hostilia silentio perspicit, explorator pacata clamore cognoscit*. Peut-être *explōrāre* est-il un ancien terme de chasse et se disait-il des battues où l'on chassait le gibier à force de cris. Ainsi, du sens de « faire une battue », on serait passé à celui de « battre le terrain ».

Un autre essai d'explication a été proposé par Cuny, Mém. Havet, p. 85 sqq., qui fait de *explōrō* un composé de **plōrō* dénominateur d'un substantif hypothétique **plōro-* « sol, terrain », apparenté à v. irl. *lár*, all. *Flur*. V. *plānus*.

to assimilate.

With accumulating research, there have been more and more indications that exploratory responses can be of two distinct classes, corresponding to these two distinct biological needs. On the one hand, when an animal is disturbed by a lack of information, and thus left a prey to uncertainty and conflict, it is likely to resort to what we may call *specific* exploratory responses. These supply or intensify stimulation from particular sources—sources that can supply the precise information that the animal misses. The condition of discomfort, due to inadequacy of information, that motivates specific exploration is what we call “curiosity.” In other circumstances, an animal seeks out stimulation, regardless of source or content, that offers something like an optimum amount of novelty, surprisingness, complexity, change, or variety. For this kind of behavior the term *diversive* exploration has been proposed. It

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Berlyne, D. E. (1966). Curiosity and Exploration. *Science*, 153(3731), 25–33.
<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.153.3731.25>

TABLE I
CHARACTERISTICS OF INVESTIGATION AND PLAY, AND MORE GENERALLY OF
SPECIFIC AND DIVERSIVE EXPLORATION

A.	Investigation	Play
1.	Synchrony of visual and tactile receptors	Desynchrony, or only transient synchrony of receptors
2.	Intent facial expression	Relaxed facial expression
3.	Stereotyped sequence of behavioral elements	Variable and idiosyncratic sequence of elements
4.	Elements of relatively long duration	Elements essentially brief
5.	Elicited by novel stimuli	Never manifest in the presence of novel stimuli
6.	Implicit query: "What does this <i>object</i> do?"	Implicit query: "What can <i>I</i> do with this <i>object</i> ?"
7.	Shows linear decrement with time	Is quadratic function of time
B.	Specific exploration	Diversive exploration
1.	Concerns those inspective, investigative responses directed to a particular source of stimulation, i.e. <i>stimulus-oriented</i> .	Concerns those activities which seem to increase stimulation irrespective of source, i.e., <i>response-oriented</i>
2.	Occurs in presence of highly stimulating (by virtue of novelty, complexity etc.) set of environmental factors	Occurs in <i>absence</i> of specific environmental stimulation
3.	Consists of consummatory response <i>to</i> stimulus—change	Consists of instrumental response <i>for</i> stimulus change
4.	Extrinsically motivated	Intrinsically motivated
5.	Characterized by response stereotypy	Characterized by response variability or entropy
6.	Occupies superordinate position in motivational hierarchy in that it can inhibit most tissue-preserving activities	Low in motivational hierarchy and can be inhibited by almost any other drive state

Hutt 1970: 169 Table I in Hutt, C. (1970). Specific and diversive exploration. *Advances in Child Development and Behavior*, 5, 119–180. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0065-2407\(08\)60466-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0065-2407(08)60466-8)